

Article

Challenges of Acid Attack Survivors

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Abstract

Women are facing violence for no other reason than that they are women. Recently in India, acid attacks have also emerged out as a form of gender based violence aimed at silencing and controlling women and young girls. Acid attacks are often directed at those women and young girls who reject the advances of men as if they have no right and liberty for rejection in the male dominated society. The perpetrators are familiar with the nature, habits and movement of girls and women on whom they intend to seek revenge and are, therefore, able to plan the attack in advance. The act rarely kills but causes severe physical, psychological and social scarring. The Penal provisions against perpetrators in India have now been strengthened but the question of eliminating easy access to acid has received little attention. This paper highlights the pathetic condition of victims who are leading dejected life aftermath of acid attack.

Keywords: Acid attack victims, psychological distress, permanent damage, the Criminal Law (Amendment) Act, 2013, NGOs.

Introduction

Acid throwing, also called an acid attack or vitriolage, is a form of violent assault. It is defined as the premeditated act of throwing acid on the body of a person "with the intention to disfigure, maim, torture, or kill". Perpetrators of these attacks throw acid at their victims, usually at their faces, burning them, and damaging skin

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tissue, often exposing and sometimes dissolving the bones. The victims of acid violence are overwhelmingly children and women and the perpetrators of the attacks are almost invariably young men, whose amorous or sexual advances have been spurned and who choose to "punish" the woman or girl in the cruelest manner. The attackers are familiar with the nature, habits and movement of girls and women on whom they intend to seek revenge and are, therefore, able to plan the attack in advance. The act rarely kills but causes severe physical, psychological and social scarring. The most common types of acid used in these attacks are sulphuric, nitric, or hydrochloric acid. The long term consequences of these attacks include blindness and permanent scarring of the face and body, along with far-reaching economic difficulties. Acid violence is a worldwide phenomenon that is not restricted to a particular race, religion or geographical location. It is estimated there may be as many as 1,000 acid attacks a year in India, incidents that can kill, maim and wreck the lives of the victims¹

The data released by Home Ministry of India shows that while a total of 57 cases with 65 victims were recorded in 2010, in 2012 the figure jumped to 85 cases with 101 victims. Delhi, Uttar Pradesh, Punjab, Haryana and Bihar together accounted for 53% of all victims. In fact, Delhi (31 victims) alone accounted for 27% of all victims (264) in the country between 2010 and 2012. Police action has had little effect in curbing the crime as evident from the fact that in the 225 cases in the given period, 318 people were arrested and 305 prosecuted² Still, attacks kept increasing year to year. This data reveals that patriarchal societies like U.P., Delhi, Punjab, Haryana and Bihar who are having worst sex ratios-accounting for the most number of victims. Arrests and prosecution have had no deterring effect on the crime which kept on rising, making it a more problem of social attitude than a law and order issue. States in the northeast, where several societies are matriarchal and women make up a large chunk of the workforce, have nil to single digit cases of acid attacks. Among larger states, Tamil Nadu has one of the best records with just one case in the past three years.

The most notable effects of an acid attack are the lifelong bodily disfigurement. According to the Acid Survivors Foundation in Pakistan, there is a high survival rate amongst victims of acid

attacks. Consequently the victim is faced with physical challenges, which require long term surgical treatment, as well as psychological challenges, which require in-depth intervention from psychologist and counselors at each stage of physical recovery. These far-reaching effects on their lives impact their psychological, social and economic viability in communities.

Health Effect

The medical effects of acid attacks are extensive. Severity of the damage depends on the concentration of the acid and the period of time before the acid is thoroughly washed off with water or neutralized with a neutralizing agent. The acid can rapidly eat away skin, the layer of fat beneath the skin, and in some cases even the underlying bone. Eyelids and lips may be completely destroyed, the nose and ears severely damaged. Though not exhaustive, their findings included: The skull is partly destroyed/deformed and hair lost. Some of other affects are-

- Ear cartilage is usually partly or totally destroyed; deafness may occur.
- Eyelids may be burned off or deformed, leaving the eyes extremely dry and prone to blindness. Acid directly in the eye also damages eye-sight, sometimes causing blindness in both eyes.
- Nose can become shrunken and deformed; the nostrils may close off completely due to destroyed cartilage.
- The mouth becomes shrunken and narrow, and it may lose its full range of motion. Sometimes, the lips may be partly or totally destroyed, exposing the teeth. Eating can become difficult.
- Scars can run down from the chin to neck area, shrinking the chin and extremely limiting range of motion in the neck.
- Inhalation of acid vapors usually create respiratory problems, exacerbated restricted airway pathways (the esophagus and nostrils) in acid patients.

In addition to these above-mentioned medical effects, acid attack victims also face the possibility of septicemia, renal failure, skin depigmentation, and even death. Skin should be grafted onto burn victims within a day or two to prevent infection.

Psychological Effect

Acid attacks are brutal, agonizing and embarrassing to victims. Because of the disfigurement caused by acid, the victim's psyches are debilitated, incapacitated, negatively affecting every aspect of their lives (Amway, 2003, p. 306).

Acid attack victims reported higher levels of anxiety, depression and scored higher on the Derriford appearance scale, which measures psychological distress due to one's concern for their appearance. Women suffered lowered self-esteem according to the Rosenberg scale and increased self-consciousness, both in general and in the social sphere. Shock, anger, self-pity and acceptance are the emotions that surface in the aftermath of an acid attack. These feeling are normal and must be accepted. Avoid blame games, families need to be supportive and let the victims grieve. Time and patience are crucial. People who learn to channelize their anger heal faster than those who got caught up in self-pity.

Victims have to undergo reconstructive surgeries. The prominent effect of an acid attack is lifelong bodily disfigurement. Consequently, the victim faces physical challenges, which require long-term surgical treatment, and psychological challenges, which require in-depth intervention from psychologists and counsellors at each stage of physical recovery.

Social Effect

Contact with acid can result in a wide range of injuries and even long term or permanent damage depending on the concentration and volume used. It can cause burns, scars, dissolving of the skin and tissues underneath and even have a corrosive effect on the bones. Many survivors have to undergo a number of surgeries and other procedures on their eyes, nose, ears and skin on the face, neck and other parts of the body.

Acid attacks usually leave victims of handicapped in some way, rendering them dependent on either their spouse or family for everyday activities, such as eating and running errands. This dependency is increased by the fact that many acid survivors are not able to find work, due to impaired vision and range of motion. This negatively impacts their economic viability, causing hardships on the families/spouses that care

for them. As a result, divorce rates are high, with abandonment by husbands

Case Studies of Acid Attack Victims

The researcher has highlighted some well known cases where girls and women have become victims of acid attack and how their life had been changed where they feel themselves as worst than handicapped and being dependent upon others. The pathetic condition of few acid attack victims are narrated below –

Case of Tapasi

A woman named Tapasi in her mid-30s was attacked with acid by a youth in Baduria, North 24 Pargana, on January 12, 2014 night. She has been admitted to a hospital with acid burn injuries. Atul Mondal, who lives in the same locality in Baduria's Kashpur, has allegedly been trying to woo the woman, who is a mother of two. According to police, the two knew each other. However the woman has been trying to ignore Atul since the past few days as he was allegedly pressuring the woman to elope with him. Atul allegedly called the woman out of home at 8.30pm on Sunday pleading that he wanted to iron out differences. Once the duo reached Kaharpara, about a kilometer away from the woman's house, he reportedly started forcing the woman to elope with him right away. On being refused, he allegedly poured acid on the woman. Local rushed to the spot on hearing the cries of the woman. Atul managed to flee. She was first rushed to Baduria state General Hospital from where she was shifted to a nursing home in Barasat³.

Case of Meena Soni

Meena survived 75 percent burns on her face and upper body. Her culprit was her husband. He had done it to her after about fifteen years of togetherness. Things were never normal between them. She belonged to a family from Lucknow and her husband lived in a town in Banda. She was the youngest among seven siblings and her parents married her off when she was just 16. She had just done her class 10. Her husband was a jewellery artist. The entire family was engaged in gold and

silver jewellery making. But soon after marriage, he quit work. She had two daughters by then and no income to feed. Things became difficult to manage and she had to move out to earn the living. He was very unwilling, but she had no other option. He was suffering from tuberculosis and could not go out to work.

Meena Soni joined Mahila Samakhyia and gradually became a reporter at Khabar Lehariya, the all-women newspaper of Banda and Chitrakoot. Her husband health improved but he had lost all interest in work. Living on her earning had become his habit. He did not want to work and stopped her from going out of the house. She was working entire day, look after the family and every day they had arguments in the house. He put allegations on her and said that she should not go out to work. But that was not possible for her. Had she not worked, her children would have died of hunger. She was a reporter and people of the area recognized her for her work.

It was a summer morning of 2004 and she was fast asleep. Her children were playing outside the house. Her husband came with a bottle of acid and threw it on her face. She woke up instantly. The burning sensation was strong enough to make her realize that she had faced an acid attack. She asked her daughter to call the rickshaw and ask him to take her to the doctor. God gave her extraordinary strength that day and she went to the hospital all alone. Thankfully, the doctor she went to was the same whom she had interviewed the previous day. He recognised her and gave her the treatment right way. She was in hospital when she came to know that her husband had attempted suicide. Maybe he was scared of the consequences that would have followed. Both of them were critical state and were shifted to the Allahabad medical college. He died on the fifth day and she stayed at the hospital for about three months, getting treated for the 75 percent burns on her face, chest and hands. Her children were sent to her in-law house. The NGOs that she worked with supported her in all possible ways. They got her the entire medical assistance that she needed. Finally she was back, but in a different shape. She stayed away from her children for two years as she worried that if they looked at her; they would get scared and might not come near her. Then she underwent another surgery at Lucknow and got her children back after two years⁴.

Case of Chanchal Kumari

Chanchal Kumari has dream of becoming computer engineer at the age 18 years. She was encouraged by to pursue her dream by her father, Saliesh Paswan. A daily wage construction worker, who barely earns enough to make the ends meet for his family of four, so unmindful of his meager earning, he enrolled Chanchal in a intermediate college and encourage to do coaching for clearing engineering entrance examination.

Life was never easy but the hope of a rewarding future kept her going. Trips from her native Chitnawan village, under Maner police station of Patna district (Bihar), to her college and coaching institute in Danapur were endless. Then, late in the night of October 21, 2012, her whole world came crashing around her. A few minutes short of midnight, four youth from her village climbed onto the roof of her single-storey *Indira Awas Yojna* house at Chitnawan, as she was sleeping there with her younger sister, Sonam. Two of them held her hands and the other two intruders poured almost a litre of acid on her face. As she writhed in agony, they laughed at her. One of them said: "Now you see we do whatever we say". These boys had been harassing her for month. They used to pass vulgar remarks, pull her *chunni* and follow her on their bike when she went to Danapur for her classes.

For months after the incident, nobody came to help victim family. Even the local *mukhia* (village headman) and the area MLA avoided visiting the families as the culprit are from a dominant community. Since then, internet campaigns by several NGOs and Maner based social activist have had many people pledging their support for my treatment and rehabilitation. Scheduled Caste Commission had given two sisters Rs 2.42 lakhs which was not enough to begin with, is long gone.

Chanchal want exemplary punishment to be handed out to the culprits so that it dissuades others like them from ruining the lives of innocent girls, who are pursuing their dream under trying circumstances.⁵

Case of Laxmi

Laxmi was from a poor family. Her father worked as a chef in a South Delhi home. She became friends with another girl in the neighbourhood and her brother soon started proposing her, she politely turned down his offer of marriage. She was only 15 and he, 32 years old. On April 22, 2005, she was waiting for a bus in a crowded Central Delhi area in daylight. He approached her with his brother's girlfriend. Before she knew it, they had flung her onto road, pinned her down and threw acid on her face. In thirty seconds, the acid had leached through to her bones, melted her ear and reduced her face to a mass of third degree burn. The pain was unbearable. It was happened in broad daylight at a busy bus stop, but no one answer her screams for help. A politician's driver took her to a hospital, where she was to stay for ten weeks. She learnt to live with the physical pain but what hurt more was the way society reacted. Her own relatives stopped seeing her, as did her friends. She stayed indoors for eight years and ventured out only in a *ghungat*. Since then, she has mostly lived indoors. She has had seven surgeries and needs four mores. Life has been all about pain and rejection⁶.

Case of Preeti Rathi

Preeti passed her class 10 exam from National Public School in Narela (Delhi) and class 12 from the Narela government school. Then she joined a four years nursing course at Laxmi Bai Batra College in Delhi and parents spent Rs5 lakh on her course. She graduates in 2011 with a first division. When her siblings were in school, Preeti helped them with their studies to save on tuition fee. After she cleared the course, Preeti did a year's internship at the Batra Hospital in Delhi and then joined the Susheela Hospital in Narela at a salary of Rs 15,000/-. With her first salary, she brought new clothes for family members. Her starting salary at naval hospital would have been Rs 40,000/- plus allowances. The day before she left for Mumbai, she said she would take family members there once she got an official accommodation.

On May 1, 2013 Preeti along with her father, uncle and aunt boarded the *Garib Rath* Express from New Delhi for Mumbai to report at

INHS Asvini. The train reached the Bandra station on time. They were looking for the nearest exit when someone tapped Preeti's shoulder from behind. She turned around. A man, his face half covered with a handkerchief, then threw acid on her face. Her father heard Preeti's scream but before he could react, the culprit fled. A few drops of acid fell on her father's hand also. For a few minutes the three stood there paralyzed, shocked by the sudden turn of events. Then they started shouting for help and asked around for the first-aid counter. There was none. She was shifted to the Masina Hospital in Byculla (East), which has a state of the art burns centre. The hospital set up 12 member's panel to plan her treatment, but her health had deteriorated by then. Her eyes were damaged, her kidneys were infected and acid had entered her oesophagus, windpipe and trachea. She could not succumb to acid injury and died. After Preeti death, family members met Maharashtra home minister R.R. Patil and pressed for an investigation by Central Bureau of Investigation (CBI). The state government agreed but Union government is still pending the file. For the family members, life has changed completely after Preeti's death⁷.

Case of Rubi Rawat

Rubi Rawat was at her parents' place in Porsa town in Morena district (MP), when Yogenrda Singh Tomar, upset after she refused to live with him, barged into the house in the early hours and poured acid on her. When Rawat's grandmother and two cousins came to her rescue, Tomar threw acid on them as well, injuring them. Rubi died a few hours later at the district hospital in Morena. "Tomar had an affair with Rubi. As she was not willing to live with him, he attacked her", Morena superintendent of police Gajendra Singh Kanwar said.

Rubi was living with her parent after her husband walked out of the marriage a year ago on getting to know of her affair, said the police. Before she move in with her parents, Rubi lived with Tomar, who, too is married. She was visiting her uncle and returned to Porsa after Tomar called her up to resolve their differences, the police said⁸

Case of Sabina Khatun

Like any other 18 years old, she was bubbly and full of zest for life. Every morning, she used to look forward to seeing her friends at school and her boy friend after the classes got over. Love is a beautiful feeling and it nourished her life. Isha Mondal and Sabina Khatun had been in a relationship for the past three years. Isha is a second year student at Fakir Chand College in Diamond Harbour(WB) and belong to her neighbouring village Kamarpole Dighipara. On the ill fated day, like any other day, she met him after school. Suddenly, he was struck by this whimsicality to marry her right away. Initially, she was taken aback by his insistence but ultimately relented. Truth be told, she wanted to spend the rest of her life with him anyway. Isha took me home around 9.30pm to meet his parents, Right from the beginning she could sense that his parents did not like her. They curtly asked her why she was visiting them so late at night. She plainly told them that their son had brought her to meet them to discuss our marriage. At this, Isha's parents told her to get out of his life but she tried to reason with them that they loved each other and wanted to get married. Isha's infuriated parents and brother, Insan and Iqbal, then started beating her up. She tried to fight back and save herself. She tried fight back and saves herself. Hearing the commotion, some neighbours rushed to their house. They enquired from Isha's family who she was and what an unknown girl like her was doing at their house so late at night.

It was almost 10 pm by then. Isha's father Iiyas told the neighbours that it was a family matter and they would settle it themselves. The neighbours then left, telling Iiyas not to hit Sabina and advice him to send her back to her parent home. But Iiyas convinced them that there was no problem and that Sabina would spend the night with Isha's mother. But the torture manifold after the neighbours went away. Isha's mother was now openly exhorting her husband and son to kill Sabina. She was already bleeding at the mouth from the beating received at their hands. Suddenly, Insan and Iqbal pinned her down to a chair and Iiyas fetched a bottle of acid. Insan was keeping her hand down and Iqbal held her cheeks, forcing her to open her mouth. Iiyas then emptied the acid bottle in her throat and forced his hand inside Sabina mouth, compelling her to swallow the

burning liquid. All this while, Isha just watching and did not utter a single word in her defense. Sabina was left to fend for herself in the face of assault by the three men. She started vomiting and soon fell unconscious. Fearing that Sabina might die, Isha's family dumped her at the Diamond Harbour sub-divisional hospital. The following morning, she was referred to the Chittaranjan Cancer Hospital at Hazra in Kolkata. She had suffered 20 per cent burns on her face, arms, chest and other part of the body.

Sabina's father registered an FIR against Ilyas, Insan and Iqbal. But police picked up only Insan and kept him in the lock-up for a couple of days, after which he was bailed out. Her father requested a speedy trial and punishment for the guilty. The case is still pending in court. Throughout this trauma, The Association for Protection of Democratic Rights helped Sabina's family members with legal counseling and also took up the matter with the West Bengal Women's Commission and police. But Sabina's family member's grievances have not been redressed till date⁹.

Case of Annu Mukherjee

She came to Delhi when she was three. Her father was a lawyer and mother, a home-maker. Her parents had decided that Annu should live with her childless aunt. Annu stayed with aunt in Mehrauli, where she studied in a Bengali school. She loved dancing and studying. Her parents died when she was 11 years and her brother, Kaushal, was barely two months old at that time. Her uncle never let her meet or see them. The aunt had proved to be a cruel woman and she found solace in two neighbourhood friends-Seema and Sapna. When it becomes impossible to live with her aunt, she moved in with them. She had to stop studying and start working to sustain her brother and her.

One day, they come across an advertisement in the *Punjab Kesari*. Rajdoot, a south Delhi hotel, was looking for girls to dance in their variety show. Annu applied and got selected. A woman named Meena Khan, a mother of two who did not earn much, was among her co-workers. One day she asked Annu to leave the job. Annu told her, "This is all she can do to earn a

living, she cannot leave". She went to police to file a complaint but the hotel owner threatened her that she would lose her job if she pressed charges against her. Meena apologized and she let the matter go.

Around 6.30 pm on December 19, 2004, she was heading for her duty and her brother was at the tuition. The hotel used to send a vehicle to pick her up and it was waiting. As she walked out, she saw Meena, her brother Qayoom Khan and some of their friends. The winter chill had just set in and they were covered in shawls. She asked Meena what they were doing there and she said in a strange tone: "*Bas tujhse milne aayi hu*". In a flash, her brother drew out an arm and threw acid on her. She screamed in shock and pain, and the passersby started pouring water and milk on her. Her clothes got burnt and her chest was exposed. An auto driver immediately covered her with his shirt and took her to Apollo Hospital. Later she was shifted to AIIMS where the word "treatment" took an altogether different meaning. She came home after spending three months in the hospital. Her brother was 13 years old and everything was over for them. She went through seven surgeries that cost her Rs 2-3 lakh. She still needs another Rs 20 lakh to get better. Eventually, the money ran out and so did her treatment.

She pursued the case in court. That was a new battle. Our justice system is slow but she finally won the case. Meena and her brother were penalized by court. But today, they are out of jail and roaming freely. Annu's life stands ruined. Her brother had to stop studying so he could support her¹⁰

Case of Haseena Hussain

Haseena Hussain is officially the first acid attack victim in Karnataka. April 20, 1999, was the day she was disfigured by a plastic jug full of sulphuric acid when a satanic man prevailed over God and reworked her face and fate. It was also the day her soul died to live in hell. She lost everything that day, including her eyes.

Before her world turned dark, she had completed a computer course while studying for the first year B. Com. She got a job at a software centre run by a former Indian Air Force employee, Joseph Rodriguez. After the centre incurred heavy losses, she left it and joined another office. Joseph wanted her to return and work at a computer set-up in his house but she rejected his offer. Joseph was obstinate. He kept pestering her with his offer. He simply refused to believe that she could not really want to return to his employment. Joseph was furious to his employment; he threatened her with dire consequences for not accepting his offer.

That fateful day, she left her house at Jalahalli (Bengaluru North-East) for office; suddenly a motorcycle-born man splashed the liquid content of a plastic jug on her and sped away. The liquid which was later confirmed as sulphuric acid made her face, eyes, neck, chest, hands, legs and cloths burn. It was as if someone had set her on fire. She cried out in excruciating pain. Some people standing nearby immediately moved her to HMT Hospital and from there to Ramaiah and finally to Victoria Hospital.

She undergoes a series of painful surgeries, each one lasting five to seven hours. The nose surgery was particularly agonizing and it took at least 10 hours. But nothing could make her see again, of each the psychological pain. She was on bed rest virtually for 10 years. During this period, her parents suffered a lot and had to even sell their house for her treatment. Her father a retired government employee and her homemaker mother were initially not in a position to bear the expansive treatment and she was therefore treated in government hospital for eight months. Even today, she cannot sit straight, walk without support. She hides her eyes behind black goggles that had dreamt of a bright life. A five year criminal trial in a lower court gave her attacker five years three months jail, beside a fine of Rs 3 lakh. He was convicted only for causing grievous hurt and not attempt to murder, the Bangalore High Court later sentenced him to life imprisonment for attempt to murder and awarded her Rs 2 lakh. The Supreme Court later upheld the High Court order¹¹

Legal Remedies

The Indian Parliament has passed the Criminal Law (Amendment) Act, 2013, with special provisions for acid victim. For the first time, acid attacks have been included under a standalone provision in the Indian Penal Code (IPC). It lays down two section namely 326A (Voluntarily causing grievous hurt by use of acid, etc.) and 326B (Voluntarily throwing or attempting to throw acid) be added to the IPC¹²

Section 326A of the Indian Penal Code stated that whoever causes permanent or partial damage or deformity to, or burn or maims or disfigures or disables, any part of the body of a person or causes grievous hurt by throwing acid on or by administering acid to that person, or by using any other means with the intention of causing or with the knowledge that he is likely to cause such injury or hurt, shall be punished with imprisonment of either description for a term which shall not be less than ten years but which may extent to imprisonment for life, and with fine: Provision that such fine shall be just and reasonable to meet the medical expenses of the treatment of the victim: Provided further that any fine imposed under this section shall be paid to the victim.

Section 326B of the Indian Penal Code stated that whoever throws or attempts to throw acid on any person or attempt to administer acid to any person, or attempts to use any other means, with the intention of causing permanent or partial damage or deformity or burns or maiming or disfigurement or disability or grievous hurt to that person, shall be punished with imprisonment of either description for a term which shall not be less than five years but which may extent to seven years, and shall also be liable to fine.

Supreme Court Verdict

In the wake of increasing acid attacks on girls and women, the Supreme Court on 18th July 2013 directed that the crime be made a non-bailable offence and enhanced to Rs 3 lakh the compensation amount for victims, even as it banned over the counter sale of the corrosive at retail outlets without maintenance of record of stock and buyers' identity.

The direction came from a Bench headed by Mr. Justice R.M. Lodha while asking states and

Union Territories to frame rules to regulate sale of acids and other corrosive substance within three months. On rehabilitation, the Bench observed that the amount which is being paid is “grossly inadequate”. The compensation amount for after-care and rehabilitation cost at present ranges between Rs 5000 and Rs 1, 50,000. “It cannot be overlooked that acid attack victims need to undergo a series of plastic surgeries and other corrective treatment. We accordingly direct that the acid attack victims shall be paid a compensation of at least of Rs 3 lakh by the state government concerned as an after-care and rehabilitation cost for such victims”, the court said. The Bench said an acid attack victim would be paid Rs 1 lakh within 15 days of the incident and “the balance of Rs 2 lakh shall be paid by the state or Union Territory concerned as expeditiously as possible and positively within two months of the incident”. The compliance of the order has to be ensured by the chief secretaries of the state and administrators of the UTS respectively¹³.

“Over the counter sale of acid is completely prohibited unless the seller maintains a log/register recording the details of the persons to whom acid is sold, the quantity sold and shall contain the address of the person to whom it is sold”, the court said in an interim order. The apex court said violation of its directions “shall attract prosecution under the Poisons Act, 1919” and “the Sub Divisional Magistrate(SDM) shall be vested with the responsibility of fining the violators and initiating prosecution”.

The Bench was hearing a Public Interest Litigation (PIL) filed in 2006 by a Delhi-based acid attack victim Laxmi who was then a minor. It also passed a slew of interim direction on various issues, including sale of acids. The court said states would frame the rules regulating the sale of acid within three months after the receipt of model rules from the Central government. Educational institutions, research laboratories and hospitals “shall maintain a register of usage of acid and file the same with local police and the Sub Divisional Magistrate (SDM)”, the judges said¹⁴.

The apex court had on July 16, 2013 issued detailed directions to all state governments and Union Territories to frame rules within three months for regulating the sale of acid. However, after repeated lapses of the deadline and only

Bihar, Jammu & Kashmir and Pondicherry making some headway, the Supreme Court issued fresh directives on December 3, 2013 to all states and Union territories to frame rules on acid sale by March of 2014.¹⁵

High Court Decision

Expressing concern over increasing number of acid attacks, Punjab and Haryana High Court on July 27, 2013 stated that the court intends to fast-track all such cases pending before subordinate courts. “We have called for information from the districts concerned regarding pending cases involving acid attacks,” observed Chief Justice Sanjay Kishan Kaul while hearing an acid attack case. The HC had taken suo motu cognizance of acid attack on Mandeep Kaur and her father Shamsher Singh on July 11, 2013 while they were on way to Moga district court to attend hearing of a case.

The Delhi Government has directed all the Government and private hospitals in the national Capital to provide “immediate and free” medical treatment to the victims of acid attack. The hospitals are also directed to ensure no patient returns without first aid and if the concerned hospital does not have the advanced medical facilities for treatment in such cases, they should refer it to other hospitals after giving the primary aid. “Duty is cast on every hospital management that no victims of acid attack will be returned without providing the victim first aid or immediate medical treatment¹⁶”

Role of NGOs

Many NGOs have risen in the areas with the highest occurrence of acid attacks. In India there are so many non-profit organizations, which offer acid victims legal, medical, counseling, and monetary assistance in rebuilding their lives

Acid Survivors Foundation India (ASFI) purports to be the leading NGO in India for prevention of acid burn violence as well as for providing support services to survivors through a network of chapters and partners by sharing knowledge, expertise and best practices. ASFI acts

as a forum for advocacy of acid related causes, endeavours to promote a social environment conducive to elimination of all forms of gender violence and espouses a firm legal basis for prosecution of offenders and prescription of national guidelines for treatment, aftercare and rehabilitation of acid survivors. Acid Survivors Trust India (AST-IND) was established in perpetuity at Kolkata as a registered nonprofit organization.

Acid Survivors Foundation (ASF) was formed in 1999 with the growing concern of the rising trend of acid violence in Bangladesh. Acid violence is a form of gender based violence that reflects and perpetuates the inequality of women in society. This form of violence cuts across cultural and religious barriers and impede on women's right to fully participate in society. It has the effect of denying women important rights such as economic well being, social well being, political participation, personal fulfillment and self worth.

The Campaign and Struggle Against Acid Attacks on Women (CSAAAW), a registered nonprofit trust, has been operating as a coalition of women's rights organisations and media activist groups that are based largely out of Bangalore, since 2003. In January 2004, the CSAAAW had organised a public hearing where women acid attack survivors and their families had shared testimonies of the inhuman actions that they had endured. The campaign also brought out a comprehensive report, titled 'Burnt but not defeated', which has captured in detail the date, time and place of various incidents, the personal details such as name, age, occupation, information regarding the family, the aftermath of the episode in terms of the duration and type of medical treatment and the expenditure.

Acid Survivors Trust International (ASTI) is the only organization whose sole purpose is to work towards the end of acid violence across the world. Recognizing the need for local knowledge and expertise in order to combat acid violence effectively

To tackle this problem, acid attack survivor Shirin Juwaley set up an NGO in Mumbai called Palash Foundation. The Palash Foundation was formed in an effort to socially and economically re-integrate people with disfigurement. **Disfigurement** is defined by Palash Foundation as an altered physical appearance which can be

congenital, due to accidents, burn injuries, surgical intervention, skin deformities, illnesses or any other reason.

Suggestions

- In most acid attack cases, the victim does not die, but her face and life is ruined. Hence, acid attacks must be dealt separately and specifically and must be categorised under heinous crime. There should be minimum sentence to be life imprisonment.
- Acid attack is a cruel and inhumane crime, which calls for immediate medical treatment to the victim, irrespective of court's decisions. But, the present laws do not stand sufficient, as many victims are exhausted with running around courts for years together after having to brave a life-long health complication because of the chemical injuries they sustain. Along with specific laws to deal with acid attack cases, there must be a provision for fast track courts too, where cases are solved within three months.
- Protection officers to deal with threats and potential risks to women's safety must be appointed to stop acid attacks.
- Acid attack victims must be given complete legal support to ensure they do not have to struggle a lot to get justice.
- The women victims of acid attacks mainly face the struggle of expensive surgeries, which hinders their appropriate and speedy treatment. Hence, government must take the responsibility of their treatment.
 - *The physical and psychological trauma following an acid attack makes life very difficult for the victims. The government must take steps to rehabilitate acid attack survivors with counseling and other provisions.*

Conclusion

Thus, the process of justice to acid attack victims remains incomplete until acid attack survivors gets immediate medical, legal and economic help along with the social acceptance. It

is not possible to ban the sale of acid in country. Acid is needed for construction work, painting and other commercial activities. What needs to be changed is the mindset and attitude of the society as acid attacks are a manifestation of gender discrimination. Government officials and police should be sensitive in dealing with acid attack survivors. People should be sensitive enough to give company to or be seen with a burn or acid attack victims. The perpetrators must be tried quickly and punished severely. And the survivors must automatically qualify for a monthly pension, concessions in using public transport, reservations in higher education and employment and other benefits similar to those given to people with disabilities so that the survivors can try to lead a normal life.

Notes

- ¹ . “SC Curbs Acid Sale, Order More Money for Victims”, *Hindustan Times*, Calcutta July 20, 2013, p-1.
- ² “Worst sex ration leads to acid attacks ” *Sunday Times of India*, January 12,2014,p.7
- ³ “Woman Burnt with Acid”, *The Times of India*, Kolkata, January 14, 2014 p-3.
- ⁴ “Acid Attack Kills 28 Years Old in MP”, *Hindustan Times*, Calcutta, July 23, 2013. p-9.
- ⁵ “I Was Seen Only as a Commodity”, *Hindustan Times*, Calcutta, July 24, 2013. p-10.
- ⁶ “Don’t Stare at Me : I am Human Too”, *Hindustan Times*, Calcutta, July 22, 2013, p-7.
- ⁷ “I Was Seen Only as a Commodity”, *Hindustan Times*, Calcutta, July 24, 2013. p-10.
- ⁸ Ibid
- ⁹ . “They Emptied an Acid Bottle in my Throat”, *Hindustan Times*, Calcutta, July 28, 2013 p-2.
- ¹⁰ . “SC Curbs Acid Sale, Order More Money for Victims”, *Hindustan Times*, July 20, 2013, Calcutta, p-1.
- ¹¹ “I Was Seen Only as a Commodity”, *Hindustan Times*, Calcutta, July 24, 2013. p-10.
- ¹² . Vide “The Criminal Law (Amendment) Act” Government of India, 2013.
- ¹³ . “SC Increases Acid Attacks Payout to Rs 3 Lakh”, *The Times of India*, Kolkata, July 19, 2013, p-1.
- ¹⁴ “SC Bans Over the Counter Acid Sale”, *The Statesman*, Kolkata, July 19, 2013. p-4
- ¹⁵ Worst sex ration leads to acid attacks ” *Sunday Times of India*, January 12,2014,p.7
- ¹⁶ . “Treat Acid Attack, Rape Victims For Free: Government”, *The Pioneer*, New Delhi, January 24, 2014.